

Isolation of magnetic material from fly ash and its catalytic performance for *N*-acetylation under solvent free conditions

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Abstract : Coal fly ash is a waste material generated in huge amount due to burning of coal for the generation of electricity. Magnetic material isolated from fly ash was characterized by XRD, FT-IR, SEM-EDS, XPS, BET and TEM techniques. It is used as heterogeneous catalyst for the *N*-acetylation reactions of amines with carboxylic acids. The present methodology is environmentally benign, cost effective and offers several advantages, like excellent yields, short reaction times, reusability of catalyst and simple work up procedure. The case studies cover new approaches and experiments, which will articulate the requirement for industrial application of sustainable chemistry.

Keywords : Fly ash, magnetic heterogeneous catalyst, *N*-acetylation of aniline.

Introduction

Coal fly ash is waste product of coal combustion in a coal – fired power stations. Large quantity of coal fly ash is produced in thermal power plants throughout the world every year. The amount of coal fly ash formed is approximately 500 million tones per year and likely to increase. The global recycling rate of fly ash is only 15%¹. It is being consumed in the production of construction materials, in agriculture, metal recovery, in water and atmospheric pollution control, etc.². These applications could be successful up to some extent to consume part of the huge amount of fly ash. Nevertheless, the search of new applications of the fly ash as either catalyst or as catalyst support material is still ongoing. Literature survey reveals that the fly ash is used as adsorption catalyst for the removal of dyes³, heavy metals⁴ etc. Major constituents of coal fly ash are SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄. After high temperature combustion, these oxides are formed with high thermal stability. Utilization of fly ash for other industrial applications provides a cost effective and environmentally benign way of recycling this solid waste. Currently researchers have focused on how to improve the capability of fly ash through proper beneficiation techniques in order to increase its catalytic activity. Literature survey reports the catalytic role of activated or modified fly ash for different reactions such as oxidation⁵, dechlorination⁶, condensation and rearrangement

reactions⁷. Fly ash is chemically activated by acid and used for esterification⁸ etc. Separation of magnetic material from fly ash is carried out by using magnetic separation method. Magnetic nanoparticles represent a set of unique building blocks whose size and composition are tunable to meet the requirements for a range of applications including magnetic fluids, catalysis, data storage, biomedicine, and toxic waste remediation⁹. In the present work, separated magnetic material is characterized and investigated its catalytic potency for amide synthesis.

Amides represent an important class of chemicals that are especially used as intermediates for drugs and pharmaceuticals, azo and sulfur dyes, fine chemicals and as additive for hydrogen peroxide, photographic chemicals and as antioxidants¹⁰. The acylation of amine is one of the most frequently used transformation in organic synthesis as it provides an efficient and inexpensive means for protecting amino groups in multistep synthesis process. Acetyl chloride and acetic anhydride are routinely used as acylating agents in the presence of an acidic^{11,12} and basic¹³⁻¹⁶ catalysts. However, both of these reagents, being corrosive and a lacrometric in nature, are not always ideal. The use of carboxylic acid rather than acetic anhydride or acetyl chloride is both economically and environmentally advantageous. H₆P₂W₁₈O₆₂·H₂O¹⁷, anhydrous NiCl₂¹⁸ and clay K-10¹⁹ were reported for the acylation of amines respectively with acetic anhydride.

Fe- β -zeolite²⁰, Fe^{III}-montmorillonite²¹ were reported for the acylation of amine with carboxylic acids. These catalysts suffer from some drawbacks such as long reaction times, vigorous reaction conditions and the occurrence of side reactions. Here, we report a simple, selective and environmentally acceptable synthesis of amides from amines via acylation using carboxylic acid as an acylating agent and magnetic material isolated from fly ash as catalyst. The yields are quantitative and highly selective to achieve higher atom economy. There is no by-product formation except water (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

Materials :

The coal fly ash was obtained from Thermal Power Station, Parli-Vajinath, District-Beed, Maharashtra state, India. Other chemicals used were of synthesis grade reagents (Merck) and used as such, without further purification.

Isolation of magnetic material from fly ash :

The coal fly ash slurry was prepared in clean 500 mL beaker by mixing coal fly ash with deionized water in 1 : 6 wt./vol. ratio. The slurry was stirred magnetically using magnetic stir bar for 20-30 min, during stirring the magnetic material present in the slurry was attached on the surface of magnetic stir-bar, which was removed and collected several times till the magnetic material was separated completely, which was then dried in an oven at 120 °C for 2 h and used as catalytic material.

Catalyst characterization :

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of catalysts were recorded on a Bruker D8 advance X-ray diffractometer using Cu-K α radiation with a wavelength of 1.540 Å. Infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded on a FT-IR spectrometer (JASCO, FT-IR, Japan) using dry KBr as a standard reference in the range of 500–4000 cm⁻¹. The scanning electron microscopic (SEM) analyses were carried out with a JEOL JSM-6330 LA operated at 20.0 kV and 1.0 nA. The elemental composition of the metal in the

fresh fly ash and in magnetic material was estimated using an energy dispersive spectrophotometer (EDS). Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area was carried out on Quanta chrome CHEMBET 3000. X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCA-3000-VG, Uckfield, UK) was used to study the chemical composition of the sample. The morphology of material was also characterized with CM-200 PHILIPS transmission electron microscopy (TEM) operated at 200 kV and resolution, 0.23 nm. ¹H NMR spectra of *N*-acylated derivatives were recorded on a 200 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ as a solvent and chemical shifts values δ (ppm) are recorded relative to tetramethylsilane (Me₄Si) as an internal standard.

Experimental procedure :

A mixture of aniline (6 mmol), acetic acid/propionic acid (0.1 mmol) and 0.1 g magnetic material as a catalyst and reaction mixture was refluxed for 40–120 min (Scheme 1). The reaction progress was monitored using TLC (hexane/ethylacetate (7 : 3)). When reaction was complete as indicated by TLC, the reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice. The obtained product was washed with deionized water, dried and recrystallized by ethanol. The purity of the product was determined by comparison to melting points, ¹H NMR, and FTIR spectra with the literature.

Spectroscopic data of compound :

N-Phenylacetamide (3a) : m.p. 113–115 °C (lit. m.p. 113–114 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3292 (-NH), 1655 (C=O); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.14 (3H, s, -COCH₃), 7.08 (1H, m, Ar-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.25 (2H, m, Ar-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.52 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.87 (1H, s, NH).

N-Phenylpropionamide (3f) : m.p. 109–110 °C (lit. m.p. 109–110 °C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3300 (-NH), 1664 (C=O); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.23 (3H, t, CH₃ of C₂H₅), 2.38 (2H, q, CH₂ of C₂H₅), 7.08 (1H, m, Ar-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.30 (2H, m, Ar-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.54 (2H, d, Ar-H, *J* 8 Hz), 8.0 (1H, s, NH).

Results and discussion

EDS analysis :

Fresh fly ash and magnetic material was analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively by EDS method and results are shown in Table 1. Magnetically isolated material contains an increased amount of iron (33.86%) as compared to fresh fly ash (4.72%).

Table 1. Chemical compositions of fresh fly ash and magnetic material

Sr. no.	Elements	Mass % of fresh fly ash	Mass % of magnetic material
1.	O	46.98	34.07
2.	Na	0.25	0.54
3.	Al	15.08	10.92
4.	Si	28.12	20.61
5.	Fe	4.72	33.86
6.	Ca	2.18	-
7.	K	0.94	-
8.	Mg	0.48	-
9.	Ti	1.25	-
10.	Total	100	100

XRD analysis :

X-Ray diffraction analysis was performed to understand the morphological nature of the fly ash and magnetic material. Fig. 1a shows the XRD pattern for untreated fly ash. It is found that all the reflection peaks at $2\theta = 16^\circ, 20.8^\circ, 23.2^\circ, 26.3^\circ, 30.5^\circ, 33.1^\circ, 36.1^\circ, 39.2^\circ, 40.7^\circ, 42.3^\circ, 45.6^\circ, 50^\circ, 51.9^\circ, 54.5^\circ, 57.4^\circ$ and 59.8° corresponds to the (011), (-111), (-101), (021), (111), (-131), (030), (-230), (-231), (-222), (-240), (-124), (-233), (-250), (015) and (-311) planes and which indicates the crystalline monoclinic nature of fresh fly ash (JCPDS No. 860680) and lattice parameter $a = 5.0$, $b = 8.6$, $c = 8.2$ Å. Where as Fig. 1b shows the XRD pattern for magnetic material and it was found that the sharp reflection peaks at $2\theta = 33.2^\circ, 39.3^\circ, 46.2^\circ, 65.8^\circ, 75.2^\circ, 79.4^\circ, 91.4^\circ, 107.8^\circ, 111.5^\circ$ and 138.4° corre-

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of (a) fresh fly ash and (b) magnetic material.

sponds to the (104), (006), (007), (118), (217), (1110), (402), (407), (413) and (420) planes which indicates highly crystalline hexagonal structure of ferrite type material (JCPDS No. 860550) and $a = b = 5.035$, $c = 13.74$ Å.

Crystallite size determination :

The crystalline nature and the crystallite size of the sample was analyzed by X-ray diffraction data. The particle size of the material plays an important role in determining the reactivity of fresh coal fly ash and isolated magnetic material. It was observed that the particles with smaller size exhibited higher reactivity due to availability of higher specific surface area²². Generally, the crystallite size was estimated by Debye-Scherrer equation²³ ($T = 0.94\lambda/\beta \cos \theta$), where T is the particle size, λ is the wavelength, θ is the diffraction angle and β is (FWHM). The mean crystallites size of fresh fly ash is 50 nm and magnetic material is 10 nm.

XPS analysis :

Although the XRD pattern of the samples (Fig. 1b) clearly show the hexagonal structure, it is very difficult to exclude the possibility of the γ - Fe_2O_3 phase in the separated magnetic Fe_3O_4 phase similarity. XPS is one of the most effective way to distinguish the two phases because it is very sensitive to Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} cations. In Fig. 2c the levels of Fe $2p_{3/2}$ and Fe $2p_{1/2}$ have binding energies 711 and 720 eV respectively. It conform the presence of Fe_3O_4 phase^{24,25}, Fig. 2b shows binding energy of Si ($2p$) at 102.9 eV, and Fig. 2a and Fig. 2d shows absorption peaks of Al ($2p$) and O ($1s$) are at 74.84 and 531.9 eV respectively.

TEM analysis :

The TEM image (Fig. 3) shows the presence of small spherical particles. From TEM images, measured diameter of particles is ~ 10 nm, which is consistent with the results of XRD analysis. Electron diffraction pattern of magnetic material (Fig. 3d) reveals that the sample is polycrystalline, which can be indexed to the hexagonal structure of magnetic material and accord with the XRD result. TEM image also show that the magnetic material is roughly spherical in shape. Usually, spherical shapes are formed because the nucleation rate, per unit area is isotropic at the interface between the Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles²⁴. Materials are magnetic in nature as well

Fig. 2. High-resolution XPS spectra of magnetic material contains (a) Al (2p) XPS spectra, (b) Si (2p) XPS spectra, (c) Fe (2p) XPS spectra and (d) O (1s) XPS spectra.

as nano-sized particles are known to have very large surface areas hence, catalytic material will also have high surface energy. Consequently, these fine spherical particles have coated with aluminum silicate network and form aggregated nano-particles. The dark iron center and white aluminum silicate surface of particles are visible.

SEM analysis :

(Fig. 4a) SEM image of fresh fly ash shows hollow cenospheres, irregularly shaped, mineral aggregates and agglomerated particles. Similar particles were also observed in other reported micrographs⁹. SEM image of magnetic material (Fig. 4b) shows sub-angular and spheri-

cal particles, increase in spheroidal nature of the magnetic material due to the magnetic separation method.

FT-IR analysis :

The FT-IR spectrum of fresh fly ash in Fig. 5a shows a broad band at 1060 cm^{-1} is attributed to Si-O-Si stretching vibrations. Fig. 5b shows the IR spectrum of magnetic material. The bands absorptions at 1078, 784, 560, 3437 and 1634 cm^{-1} . The 1078 cm^{-1} is due to the asymmetric stretching of Si-O-Si bands of the SiO_4 tetrahedron. The 784 cm^{-1} band is composed of the contributions from Si-O-H and Si-O-Fe vibrations, and the band at 560 cm^{-1} is related with the Fe-O stretching^{26,27}. The IR spectrum of

Fig. 3. TEM images (a, b, c) of magnetic material and (d) diffraction pattern of magnetic material.

Fig. 4. SEM images of (a) fresh fly ash and (b) magnetic material.

Fig. 5. The FT-IR spectra of (a) fresh fly ash and (b) magnetic material.

magnetic material also shows a broad intense band at 3457 cm^{-1} due to hydroxyl groups on the catalyst surface and peak at 1634 cm^{-1} is attributed to bending mode ($\delta_{\text{O-H}}$)²⁸. It is assumed that during the process of burning of coal at high temperature there is conversion of Fe_2O_3 into Fe_3O_4 which may be coated around aluminosilicate framework. However, these peaks are absent in the FT-IR spectrum of the fresh fly ash (Fig. 5a) which do not possess any catalytic activity.

BET analysis :

The specific surface area of fresh fly ash and magnetic material are $1.6233\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $105\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ respectively. Thus magnetic material provided surface for reactant to adsorb and decrease the time to convert reactant to desired product.

Catalytic activity results :

Our initial experiments focused on the optimization of the amount of magnetic material by using aniline (6 mmol) and acetic acid (0.1 mmol) and variable amount of magnetic material (Table 2). It was observed that 0.1 g magnetic material effectively catalyzed the reaction with good yield. High amount of catalyst did not show considerable effect on the reaction time. The reaction also investigated using fresh fly ash which does not catalyze reaction, which was examined up to 2 h. The reaction in presence of

Table 2. Optimization the amount of magnetic catalyst for *N*-acetylation reaction^a

Entry	Magnetic material (g)	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	Without catalyst	180	No reaction
2	0.05	80	65
3	0.1	40	94
4	0.2	40	94

^aReaction condition : aniline (6 mmol), acetic acid (0.1 mmol) and magnetic material (0.1 g). ^bIsolated yields.

other catalysts such as Fe^{III} -montmorillonite, $\text{H}_6\text{P}_2\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{62}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 6 *N* HCl, $\text{NH}_2\text{NH}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Yttria-Zirconia based acid catalyst and $(\text{Py})\text{Zn}(\text{BH}_4)_2$ are shown in Table 3. These catalysts required longer reaction times as compared to magnetic material. We then examined the scope of the reaction by using various substituted anilines and acetic acid (Table 4). Aniline rings carrying either electron-donating or withdrawing substituent reacted successfully. To extend the scope of this method, the propionylation of anilines with propionic acid was car-

Table 3. Catalytic performance of different catalyst for *N*-acetylation

Sr. no.	Catalyst/Reagent	Acetyl group	Time (min)	Yield (%)	Reference
1.	Fe ^{III} -montmorillonite	Acetic acid	180	98	21
2.	H ₆ P ₂ W ₁₈ O ₆₂ ·H ₂ O	Anhydride	40	90	17
3.	6 <i>N</i> HCl	Anhydride	Not mention	93	29
4.	NH ₂ NH ₂ ·H ₂ O	Acetic acid	180	93	30
5.	Yttria-Zirconia based acid catalyst	Acetic acid	120	93	31
6.	(Py)Zn(BH ₄) ₂	Acetic acid	150	97	32
7.	Fresh fly ash	Acetic acid	120	-	Present work
8.	Magnetic material	Acetic acid	40	94	Present work

Fig. 6. % yields of reaction on various milli mole of aniline with acetic acid.

the product remained nearly same, this indicates that if the reaction is to be carried out in large scale, it is neces-

Table 4. Acylation of amines using carboxylic acid over 0.1 g magnetic material catalyst^a

Entry	R	R ₁	Time (min)	Yields (%) ^b	M.p. (°C)	
					Observed	Literature
3a	H	CH ₃	40	94 (94,92,90,90) ^c	113–115	114 [33]
3b	4-Cl	CH ₃	60	90	177–178	179 [33]
3c	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	60	90	144–146	146 [33]
3d	4-OCH ₃	CH ₃	40	85	129–130	130 [33]
3e	Naph-1-amine	CH ₃	40	92	162–163	163 [33]
3f	H	C ₂ H ₅	80	92	109–110	108–110 [30]
3g	4-Cl	C ₂ H ₅	120	90	150–152	150–153 [30]
3h	4-CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	120	90	132–134	132–135 [30]
3i	4-OCH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	90	92	155–156	155–158 [30]
3j	Naph-1-amine	C ₂ H ₅	90	85	198–200	200–201 [30]

^aReaction condition : 1 (6 mmol) and 2 (0.1 mmol), 0.1 g magnetic material catalyst.

^bIsolated yield.

^cYield after consecutive cycles.

ried out under identical conditions. It was found that variety of amines could be efficiently propionylated in good yields as shown in Table 4. From the industrial point of view, the role of catalyst is very important, therefore, we have studied the *N*-acylation reaction at various milli mole of aniline and acetic acid, and observed that the desired product is in range (94–85%) (Fig. 6). While performing the laboratory scale reaction of *N*-acylation using variable amounts of catalyst, the reaction time and yield of

sary to use the amount of the catalyst in proportion to the initial amount of the reactants so as to complete the reaction in the stipulated time with the same yield. The magnetic material was regenerated by simple method and retained the same catalytic activity. The catalyst was washed with *n*-hexane and dried at 60 °C and activated at 120 °C for 1 h before reuse in next reaction cycle under similar reaction conditions as earlier. The reusability of the catalyst was investigated for the aniline and acetic acid. The

regenerated catalyst showed similar catalytic activity till 4th reaction cycle with almost consistent activity (Table 4). In summary, a concise, high yielding *N*-acetylation and *N*-propionylation reactions were carried out with significant yields using magnetic material. The significant features of this methodology includes : 94% yield of the product by using non-hazardous catalyst obtained from waste fly ash facile operation and non-toxic acylating agents.

Conclusions :

We have demonstrated the use of carboxylic acids as acylating agents instead of expensive acid anhydrides in presence of magnetic material to achieve optimum yields for the first time. In our methodology, notable aspect of effluent treatments does not arise as water is the only by-product. The advantages include the operation simplicity, recyclability of the catalyst, high atom economy and the mild reaction conditions. The present heterogeneous catalytic system may be potential candidate not only for laboratory practices but also for commercial applications and offers an environmentally safer alternative to the existing processes. We believe that this method will present a better and more alternative to the existing methodologies for selective acylation of amines and thus will find useful application in the synthesis of complex natural products where selective protection of hydroxyl, thio and amino groups are required.

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